

Visualizing Literary Theories through Mysskin's Pisasu

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Abstract

Students find difficult to read and understand the literary theories so the aim of the paper is to produce the best way to understand the theories. There are theories in English Literature for criticizing the literary works. Deconstruction is a criticism to erase the boundary between binary oppositions like horror/fear or revenge. This is found in the title of Mysskin's movie, Pisasu, suggests a change of pace. It upends the trope of love at first sight. Especially on a ghost a boy could fall in love with, a father could fall in love with, a mother-in-law could fall in love with. Reader-response theory is also a criticism which motives readers as an active agent for creating their own, unique, text-related understanding and gives real existence to the work and fulfils its meaning through interpretation. This can be witnessed through the character Pachai whose colour blindness leads the movie.

Keywords: autistic, signifier, abortive, aberrant, exorcise, trample

Literary Theories are the tools to understand literature practically. Theories reveals what literature can mean instead the meaning of the work of literature. It elaborates the relationship between author and work in all aspects and even in all genres. It offers different approaches for understanding the role of literal context in interpretation as well as the pertinence of linguistic and insensible elements of text.

Deconstruction is a critique that tells the relationship between text and meaning which is originated by the philosopher Jacques Derrida. Derrida's approach consists the readings of texts with intended meaning or structural unity of a particular text. The purpose of deconstruction is to show the language usage in a given text and language as a whole. He inspires from the work of Ferdinand de Saussure, language as a system of signs and words only has meaning because of the contrast between these signs. Then a concept must be understood in the context of its opposite, such as staff/para-staff, nutrition/malnutrition, open/close, etc. One of the two terms governs the other or has the upper hand: signified over signifier; nutrition over malnutrition; staff over para-staff; open over close, etc. The first task of deconstruction is to find and overturn these oppositions inside a text but the aim of deconstruction is not to strengthen all oppositions, because it is assumed that they are structurally necessary to produce sense. The oppositions simply cannot be adjoined once and for all. The authority of dual oppositions always demonstrates itself. Deconstruction only points to the significant of continuous analysis that can make clear decisions and arbitrary violence intrinsic to all texts.

For example, the word trunk derives its meaning more as a function of how it differs from bin, box, caddy, casket, case, locker, chest etc. than how the word trunk may be tied to a certain image of a traditional trunk box (i.e., the relationship between signified and signifier), with each term being established in correlative determination with the other terms. There have been problems in defining deconstruction. Derrida said that all of his essays were offers to define what deconstruction is, and that deconstruction is necessarily complicated and difficult to explain since it actively criticises the very language needed to explain it.

Derrida initially resisted granting to his approach the overarching name deconstruction, on the grounds that it was a precise technical term that could not be used to characterize his work generally. Nevertheless, he eventually accepted that the term had come into common use to refer to his textual approach, and Derrida himself increasingly began to use the term in this more general way.

The application of deconstruction in Myskin's *Pisasu*. The opinion about ghost is different from the opinion of Myskin's *Pisasu*. *Pisasu* means ghost. Usually ghost means to take revenge, kills others, attacks, or fulfils its wishes through others whereas Myskin's *Pisasu* is the one who loves a boy, who accidentally kills her and she turns as ghost. Siddharth is a protagonist who hits upon an accident where a teenage girl is lying in blood shed. He hurries her to the hospital with the help of an auto driver and a couple. However, he is too late and the girl checks out holding his hand. Thought of the incident Siddharth comes home with one of her slippers. Then he drives around the city aimlessly with his red car while helping poor people and he can't able to come out of depression due to the girl's death. After the incident, strange things start happening at his apartment. He begins to feel a supernatural presence at his house. The house is cleaned up even if he makes it messy and his bottle opener goes missing whenever he tries to drink beer. The *Pisasu* (ghost) doesn't want him to drink or smoke. With the help of his friend Badri, he brings a physic to exorcise the ghost, but she couldn't send it out. Siddharth also comes to realise that his one of the neighbour's autistic son plays with an imaginary friend. When Siddharth's mother, Janaki comes to visit him, she is attacked by a drunken neighbour, who is abusing his wife. The neighbour is then attacked by the ghost. The following day, Janaki meets an aberrant accident in the bathroom and the ghost saved her by alerting the neighbours. But, Siddharth misunderstands that the ghost had attacked his mother and threatens the ghost that he would kill himself and come as a ghost to take revenge on her. Many rituals of various religions were performed to get away the ghost from his apartment but everything is proven abortive and the ghost continues to stay. The *Pisasu* doesn't want to leave him because it loves him especially love at first sight.

Siddharth is confirmed that the ghost of the girl whose life to be saved so that all of these strange occurrences and goes in search of her family to get rid of her. He finds that girl's name is Bhavani and her father runs a local ice factory. Siddharth tells the truth to her father and asks him to cremate his daughter to save him from her ghost. Siddharth brings the father to his apartment to show him the ghost. At that time his mother calls from the hospital to tell him that it was actually the ghost who has saved her life. Bhavani's father then tries to see if the ghost is actually trying to protect Siddharth. When the ghost appears as expected, her father begs her to come home with him, but she continues to remain at the apartment. Because it wants to stay with him. Siddharth understands that Bhavani's spirit never meant him any harm. So this is the ghost loved by a boy, a mother-in-law, a father and and who are all know about it. Realizing that Siddharth with the help of his friends wants Bhavani's soul to rest in peace in order to find the killer to face justice. Later he realizes that he is the killer, Siddharth goes to tell Bhavani's father the truth. At that time the ghost tries to stop him, but he still reveals the truth. Trample with guilt, Siddharth tries to suicide himself. But Bhavani's spirit saves him by cremating her own body that her father had preserved all this time in the ice.

Thus it moves to the next world. Bhavani's father encounters Siddharth by saying that he is a very kind hearted person that is why his daughter fell in love with him and stayed with him and he would have never done the accident intentionally.

Reader-response theory is a literary theory that focuses on the reader or audience and their experience of a literary work or movie or any genre. It allows the readers to create their own meaning for the text and the readers as an active agent who make actuality or reality to the work and fulfils its meaning through interpretation. Reader-response criticism assert that literature should be viewed as a performing art in which each reader creates their own unique, text-related work or performance. Readers are inclined to interpret at the time of reading. The most primary difference among reader-response critics is probably those who regard individual differences among readers' responses as important and those who try to get around them. Reader-response critics support in order to understand a text to readers who create meaning and experience. Formalism is one of the text-oriented school often thinks about reader-response criticism as an anarchic subjectivism which allows readers to interpret a text any way they want.

When Siddhartha track down the auto driver with other auto drivers who are mocking the driver by calling him as Pachai instead of his real name. Here we can find the audience role to understand the director's intention that why is mockingly called as Pachai. Later the protagonist finds the driver and enquired about the accident. He tells them that he saw a green car driving away after the accident. They then manage to track down the green car at a shady workshop. There through the driver's cousin, who was in the car at the time of the accident tells Siddharth that she saw the actual car that hit Bhavani that day and that it was not green but red. Siddharth then goes back to the auto driver and asks him to differentiate between red apples and green ones, which he cannot identify. This incident shows the interpretation of audience. The director of the movie lets the audience to find the meaning and it is witnessed the driver's colour blind later it is revealed that he could see only green colour to the audience in one the scenes.

Visualizing the literary theories are easier than reading it. Nowadays students feel difficult to read and understand the literary theories because the influence of mass media among them reduced their reading habits especially reading of text. They concentrate only on the prescribed syllabus materials like summary, story, concept. So we can use visual examples to teach theories. Specifically if it is in a movie or a literary movie they can easily understand and couldn't forget it. So, one of the best ways to teach literary theories is through visuals such as Deconstruction and Reader-Response Theory in Myskin's Pisasu.